

09 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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22 January 2021

The paper is the ninth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>.

The post is about the meaning of the proposed existence of spacetime in the theory of special and general relativity compared to the proposed underlying structure of the units of discrete space.

The concept of relative time

The concept of relative time originates from the conclusion that a beam of light has a constant velocity and doesn't act instantaneous. The consequence is that 2 sources of light that are at different distances of an observer can emit a short light pulse that is seen by the observer at exactly the same moment, suggesting a non existing simultaneity at the moment of emission by both light sources. So we need [Minkowski space](#) to create reference frames and [Lorentz transformations](#) to relate events with different reference frames. But that's not the nature of relative time because this is about the synchronization of events with the help of a single time registration in relation to the involved observer(s). Actually, it is about the mutual relations of the observable phenomena.

Relative time^[1] is the observation that clocks will not run synchronously if the clocks don't share the same local physical conditions. For example a clock that is moving with a moderate speed and another clock at high speed. An observation that is verified by experiments with atomic clocks but also with particles that have a fixed time of decay. So if the decaying particle is accelerated to nearly the

figure 1

speed of light, the duration of the decay is lengthen. An observation that is comparable with the well known [twin paradox](#). A paradox that is caused by Albert Einstein's statement that time is what a clock shows. But that is not a description of the nature of time, it is mere an assumption to avoid a difficult explanatory concept.

figure 2

Figure 1 (see **08**) – or the more simple version in figure 2 – shows in a schematic way the loop of an amount of concentrated quanta (mass) at a certain moment ($E = m c^2$). If the concentration of quanta is passed on to nearly the speed of light every unit has to transfer quanta in the *direction of the motion* of the concentration. As a result the transfer of quanta within the “closed” loop has nearly stopped. But if a concentration of energy shows hardly changes at its boundary in relation to the changes in other local physical conditions it is like phenomenological time has slowed down. And clocks are energy concentrations too. In other words, there is no twin paradox. The cause behind all the confusion is the limited point of view we use in phenomenological physics.

So relative time describes the observable changes of the phenomena if the local physical conditions have changed. It doesn't replace or extend the properties of the constant of time (t_c), see **03**. The constant of time is the “building block” of relative time.

References:

1. Albert Einstein (2001). “*Relativity: The Special and the General Theory*” (Reprint)
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The concept of the curvature of space itself

In physics there exists the doctrine that the outcome of experiments determine the reliability of a hypothesis. But the statement suggests that the hypothesis and the experiment are developed in an independent way. But that is not always true because Albert Einstein had the aim to insert Newtonian gravity in his theory of relativity. Therefore he used Newton's gravitational constant in his theory of general relativity although there is hardly evidence that his model of curved spacetime describes Newtonian gravity.

If I examine the cause behind the emergence of a field of gravitation – the decrease of a local scalar in the centre of a concentration of energy (a rest mass carrying particle) – the force of gravitation is the vectorization of the flat Higgs field (08). Scalar vectors that point in the direction of the decreased scalar from vacuum space around and act instantaneous. The scalar vectors are like the vectors of the magnetic field that determine the direction of the transfer of quanta in vacuum space by the electric field.

The influence of the scalar vectors of Newtonian gravity in vacuum space is determined by the distance between the decreased scalar(s) and the position of the probe. An influence that can be symbolized with the help of concentric shells around the object, the red circles in figure 3. Concentric shells that represent the local mutual relations between the electric field and the magnetic and gravitational vectors. Physical relations that influence the trajectory of every “tangible” phenomenon in the universe.

In other words, it is really difficult to argue that Newtonian gravity has no relations with the theoretical framework of modern quantum physics.

figure 3

Einstein's theory of [General relativity](#) was constructed with the help of quite different concepts. First of all, Einstein noticed that a person in an accelerating space rocket (or elevator) could not determine the difference between the force of gravity and the force of accelerating. That's why the brown box inside the accelerating space rocket stands firmly on the floor (figure 4). And if a light beam can pass through a small hole in the hull of the accelerating rocket the observer will notice that the trajectory of the light beam inside the rocket seems to be curved because the point of reflection on the opposite side is not at the same height as the small hole in the hull of the accelerating rocket.

figure 4

The motion of objects in space is the transfer of concentrations of quanta ($E = m c^2$). In other words, the object as a local concentration is moving within a volume of space with the same *basic* field properties. There is the electric field, the magnetic field and the Higgs field. And because of the existence of the object the flat scalar field around the nuclei of the object is vectorized (Newtonian gravitation).

Is inertial mass and gravitational mass [equivalent](#)? Inertial mass represents a number of units of discrete space that holds for a moment an amount of topological deformation that is much higher in relation to the other units around. To transfer all these concentrated quanta in a linear way there must be some kind of a vector field to determine the linear transfer. And gravitation is a vector field too.

But there is not only equivalence between inertial mass and gravitational mass because electrostatic mass is part of the equivalence too. Actually every mass that is transferred by a distinctive force. Therefore, Einstein's choice to dedicate space itself as the one and only medium (causation) of the

force of gravitation is not founded on a reliable supposition. However, experiments contradict this opinion.

The electric field at the macroscopic scale

In the microcosm the electric field is the deformed part of every unit of discrete space. A unit represents the scalar mechanism and the never ending amplitudes of the electric field are the topological transformations of the deformed parts of the units. The general mechanism behind all the transformations is the never ending “effort” of every unit to get the shape of a full scalar in relation with the absence of a static balance between the units.

The general mechanism creates local concentrations of topological deformation – like mass carrying particles – but that doesn’t mean that the cause behind the concentration of topological deformation is vanished. In other words the electric field at the macroscopic scale is still concentrating quanta. But the concentration of quanta is a step by step process between the units of discrete space because all the quanta transfer in the universe is synchronized and conserved. If there is too much disturbance by radiation – electromagnetic waves, high energy particles – the step by step mechanism is interrupted. Moreover the existing concentrations of quanta – stable rest mass carrying particles – don’t have the speed of light thus slow matter is obstructing the process of concentration too (figure 2).

The electric field at the macroscopic scale represents a small force – a “residue” electric force – that concentrates matter too. It can be imagined like concentric shells around matter because matter is at the centre of the process of concentrating quanta.

figure 5

The conclusion is that Newtonian gravity and the “residue” electric force are both responsible for the concentration of matter. Einstein imported the gravitational constant (G) in the equations of his theory of General relativity but his concept of the curvature of space itself doesn’t correspond with Newtonian gravity. So it is obvious to conclude that

Einstein’s curved spacetime isn’t equal to the force of Newtonian gravity.

Einstein described the “residue” electric force – acting with the speed of light – at the macroscopic scale and he thought that matter is the cause behind the curvature of “space”. But the “residue” electric force is a push force from vacuum space around and it creates mainly local “clouds” of mass within vacuum space (the flat Higgs field). Concentrations of topological deformation that we have termed “Dark matter”.^[2]

Figure 5 shows the relation between the invariant volume and the variable surface area of 1 unit of discrete space. But all the units of discrete space transform their shape synchronously. Therefore figure 5 doesn’t represent only the relation of 1 unit, it shows the whole universe too.

The result of the “effort” of every unit of discrete space to get the shape of a full scalar is the concentration of topological deformation. The result is the decrease of the average topological deformation of most of the units of discrete space (green arrow) and the concentrated local surplus of topological deformation represents mass and rest mass (blue arrow).

It seems a bit strange but this doesn’t mean the “rehabilitation” of Newtonian gravity. Because the orbits of celestial bodies are not primary caused by Newtonian gravity.

References:

1. J.C. Kapteyn (1922). "First attempt at a theory of the arrangement and motion of the sidereal system". *Astrophysical Journal* 55: 302-327. DOI: 10.1086/142670